

METHODS OF FORMATION OF PRIMARY ENGLISH COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The paper reveals the approaches for formation of primary English communication skills in primary school. According to surveys of communicative teaching of the English language acquire special significance, since communication skills act as the achievement of a practical result in mastering English language, as well as in the education, upbringing and development of the student's personality. It is essential that primary communicative skills are being formed with the aid of increasing vocabulary, pronunciation skills, speaking proficiency in elementary situations of communication in the context.

The process of mastering communication skills is a repeated performance of foreign language actions aimed at automation in various types of speech activity and communication in a foreign language. Let us first dwell on the content of teaching a foreign language in primary school. It implements the main goals aimed at developing a culture of primary communication skills in schoolchildren in the process of developing communication skills. These skills involve the formation of both purely linguistic skills (lexical, phonetic, grammatical), and their normative use in oral and written speech [1,3]. Various topics, texts, problems, speech tasks are focused on the formation of different types of speech activity, the development of socio-cultural skills and

abilities, which ensures the use of a foreign language as a means of communication. When studying a foreign language in primary school, the focus is on the consistent and systematic development of students' primary communication skills in the process of mastering various strategies of speaking, reading, listening and writing [4].

Teaching a foreign language in primary school is aimed at studying it as a means of international communication through [6]:

- Formation and development of basic primary communication skills and abilities in the main types of speech activity;
- Socio-cultural development of schoolchildren in the context of culture with the help of regional, cultural and linguistic-cultural material;

Communication skills are formed on the basis of:

- a) language knowledge and skills;
- b) linguistic and regional knowledge [5].

Communication skills include the following critical skills:

- read and understand simple, authentic texts (with an understanding of the main content and with full understanding);
- to communicate verbally in standard situations of educational, labor, cultural, household spheres;
- orally, briefly tell about yourself, the environment, retell, express an opinion, assessment.
- the ability to write and convey elementary information (letter).

This is how the minimum level of communication skills in the state educational standard for foreign languages is determined [7].

In the process of verbal communication, people use the means of language - its vocabulary and grammar - to build statements that would be understandable to the addressee. However, knowledge of only vocabulary and grammar is not enough for communication in a given language to be successful: teachers also need to know the conditions for using certain linguistic units and their combinations. In other words, in addition to grammar itself, a native speaker must learn "situational grammar" [4], which prescribes to use the language not only in accordance with the meaning of lexical units and the rules for their combination in a sentence, but also depending on the nature of the relationship between the speaker and the addressee, on the purpose of communication and from other factors, the knowledge of which, together with the

actual linguistic knowledge, constitutes the level of the communication skills of a native speaker [2].

The changes take place today in public relations, means of communication require an increase in the communicative competence of schoolchildren, improvement of their philological training, therefore, the study of the English language as a means of communication and generalization of the spiritual heritage of the countries of the studied language and peoples has acquired a priority importance. Foreign language teachers are faced with the task of forming a personality that will be able to participate in intercultural communication [3].

The nature of communication skills included in the communicative competence and differing from knowledge of the language itself can be illustrated by the example of the so-called indirect speech acts [1]. An indirect speech act is a speech act whose form does not correspond to its real meaning in a given situation.

For example,

If a neighbor at the dinner table addresses to each other with the following words:

- Could you give me the salt ?,

Then in form this is a question, but in essence it is a request, and the answer to it should be action: you pass the salt shaker to your neighbor. If understanding this request as a question and answer: - *I can, without taking the appropriate action and waiting for the interlocutor to really directly ask you to give him the salt,* - the communication process will be disrupted: you will not act as the speaker expected and how it is customary to react to such questions - requests in similar situations. [5].

Also, in the process of communication, there is an orientation towards the social characteristics of the speech partner: status, position, situational role, which is manifested in the choice of alternative speech means with stratifications and speech constraints. Both grammatical and lexical skills and abilities represent the center of linguistic competence on which speech skills and abilities are based. Communication forms a person as a person, gives him the opportunity to acquire certain character traits, interests, habits, inclinations, to master the norms and forms of moral behavior, to determine the goals of life and choose the means of their realization. Under the identity of S.L. Rubenstein understands *the totality of developed habits and preferences, sociocultural experience and acquired knowledge that determine everyday behavior ...* [8].

When organizing the communication process, an important role is played by taking into account the personal and age characteristics of younger students. Younger school age is extremely favorable for mastering communication skills in English lessons. Primary school age (6–10 years old) is characterized by readiness for school education, which is based on an interest in new activities, which is a source of motivation for learning. A child's readiness for school is determined by his possession of a sufficient amount of knowledge in the field of everyday communication, culture and behavior, the ability to cooperate, and the desire to learn. These qualities are formed in the family, in the preschool years, and the child's entry into school life, his attitude towards school and the success of his studies largely depend on the level of their formation [9].

Researchers note a number of difficulties faced by junior schoolchildren: a new mode of life, the need to work systematically to acquire knowledge, and acceptance of the authority of a teacher.

Many methodologists consider early foreign language classes to be preferable for reaching a basic level of mastery of communication skills. The primary school age is the most optimal in the acquisition of a foreign language. In this case, the task remains in the field of vision, which the initial training in this subject is intended to solve, namely the development of communication skills. This presupposes that schoolchildren have not only practical skills, but also certain personality traits: sociability, relaxedness, the desire to make contact, the ability to interact in a team, and so on. Of course, we are not talking about how to develop children at the expense of knowledge, but about how the development of communication skills was specifically aimed at developing the personality of younger students.

Opportunities of English lessons in the formation of communication skills among primary schoolchildren - The possibilities of English lessons in the formation of communication skills among younger students are extremely wide. First of all, formulating the goal of teaching a foreign language to primary schoolchildren. The main goal of teaching foreign languages at school is to develop the student's ability to communicate in a foreign language. The implementation of this goal is associated with the formation of a number of communication skills among students: to understand and generate foreign language statements in accordance with a specific communication situation, speech task and communicative intention;

carry out their communicative behavior in accordance with the rules of communication and the national and cultural characteristics of the country of the target language.

At the first stage of education (in grades II – IV), the following goals are realized:

- to promote earlier introduction of younger students to a new language world for them at an age when children do not yet experience psychological barriers in using a foreign language as a means of communication;
- to form in children a readiness to communicate in a foreign language and a positive attitude towards its further study;
- to form elementary communication skills in four types of speech activity (speaking, listening, reading, writing), taking into account the speech capabilities and needs of younger students;
- to acquaint junior schoolchildren with the world of foreign peers, with foreign song, poetic and fairy tale folklore and with samples of children's fiction available to children in the foreign language being studied;
- to introduce children to a new social experience using a foreign language by expanding the range of social roles played in game situations typical for family, everyday, educational communication, to form ideas about the most general features of speech interaction in the native and foreign languages, about the morals that are of interest to younger schoolchildren and customs of the countries of the target language;
- to form some universal linguistic concepts observed in the native and foreign languages, thereby developing the intellectual, speech and cognitive abilities of students. [9,10]

The new basic curriculum provides for the compulsory study of a foreign language from grade II to grade IV in primary school with 2 hours a week. Considering the results of more than forty years of research in the field of early learning, which were carried out in our country in parallel with broad experiential learning, it can be argued that the benefits of English lessons in the formation of communication skills in younger students have been repeatedly proven. Briefly summarizing the advantages of systematic teaching children a foreign language at primary school age, we can note the possibilities of English lessons:

- an undeniable positive effect on the development of the child's mental functions: his memory, attention, thinking, perception, imagination, etc.;
- stimulating effect on the general speech abilities of the child;
- early teaching of a foreign language has a great practical effect in terms of improving the quality of knowledge of the first foreign language, creates a basis for continuing its study in basic school, and also opens up opportunities for teaching a second (third) foreign language, the need for proficiency in which is becoming more obvious;
- the educational and informative value of early teaching of a foreign language is indisputable, which is manifested in the earlier entry of the child into the common human culture through communication in a new language for him. At the same time, the constant appeal to the child's experience, taking into account his mentality, his perception of reality allows children to better understand the phenomena of their own national culture in

comparison with the culture of the countries of the language being studied.

Early learning of foreign languages provides students with the opportunity to develop the following communication skills:

- correctly pronounce and distinguish by ear sounds, words, phrases and sentences of a foreign language; observe the intonation of the main types of sentences;

- master the most common vocabulary within the framework of the initial stage, master a productive lexical minimum in the amount of at least 500 lexical units. The total volume of vocabulary, including the receptive lexical minimum, is at least 600 lexical units;

- get an idea of the main grammatical categories of the target language, recognize the learned vocabulary and grammar when reading and listening, and use them in oral communication;

- to understand by ear the speech of a teacher, classmates, the main content of lightweight texts based on visual clarity and linguistic guess;

- to participate in dialogical communication: to conduct an etiquette dialogue and an elementary two-way dialogue-questioning in a limited range of situations of everyday communication;

- to speak briefly on the topics selected for elementary school, to reproduce by heart the familiar rhymed works of children's folklore;

- master the technique of reading aloud; to read educational and lightweight authentic texts silently, using the techniques of introductory and study reading;

- write a short congratulation and personal letter (based on a sample), fill out a simple questionnaire about yourself;

- to master basic information about the country of the target language.

The principle of speech orientation is that the path to practical mastery of speaking as a means of communication lies through the practical use of language. The more the exercise resembles real communication, the more beneficial it is. Only lessons in English are legal. Of course, at the initial stage, it is impossible to conduct a lesson only in English, but phrases that are repeated from lesson to lesson (greetings, commands, assignments, etc.) are voiced in English initially. As an example, I give speech exercises (greeting), with which I begin my lesson in all grades, including the second grade, beginning to learn English. It should be noted that with the second grade I study this charging in parts for a month.

Greetings (3 minutes, 2–3 grades)

- T: Good morning, children!

- P: Good morning, teacher!

- T: I'm glad to see you.

- P: We're glad to see you, too.

- T: Sit down, please. How are you today?

- P: We are fine today. And you?

- T: I am OK, thank you.

It is pertinent to note that the Internet, computers with CDs, TV programs, newspapers, magazines, etc. can also be used to form a foreign language primary communicative competence. These tools serve as sources of information on the culture, history, and traditions of the countries of the target language. Through the Internet, schoolchildren can participate in contests, competitions, testing, international Internet projects,

and use e-mail to correspond with their peers who are native speakers. All this contributes to an increase in the level of language proficiency.

Thus, at present there are many methods, as well as information and communication tools, for the formation of English-speaking communicative competence. However, mastering English as a means of communication outside the

environment where it is spoken, in addition, requires the creation of imaginary situations, the compilation of entertaining tasks that can arouse the student's interest in the topic of the lesson and stimulate communication in English with requiring knowledge, skills, experience, creativity and diligence of the teacher and his pedagogical skills.

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